

1 Social systems induce extreme contrasts on evolutionary speed in
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8 Abstract

9 Sociality has been suggested as a source of differences in evolvability between species, but
10 predictions are lacking concerning the effects of different social dimensions. Using computer
11 simulations, we provide a grain of salt in this direction. We varied four parameters along four social
12 dimensions: Organization - 1) which sex disperses and 2) the number of males and females; Structure
13 and Mating systems - 3) the levels of reproductive skew among males and females; and Care systems
14 - 4) the presence or absence of cooperative care. This social variation was simulated according to the
15 genetic transmission of some of the major taxa studied, haplodiploidy and diplodiploidy to emulate
16 mammals, birds and Hymenoptera. To measure the impact on anagenesis, we assessed the spread of
17 a hyper-successful variant in an alpha individual after three generations. We hypothesized that the
18 higher this capacity for spread, the faster the speed of change in a species. To investigate
19 cladogenetic effects, we measured the number of genetic lines that reproduced and the equitability
20 of their contribution as a measure of how much mixing induced different social systems. We
21 hypothesized that the more diversity the less chances of speciation to ensue.

22 Variant spread and genetic diversity were strongly negatively correlated but showed their highest
23 variation at different sites. Spread varied most at high group sizes while diversity changed most at
24 the low end of the spectrum. Anagenesis and cladogenesis were the result of complex interactions
25 between our social variables, endorsing recent claims for the need to measure social systems along
26 multiple dimensions. We found that the number of breeding females in a unit and the level of
27 reproductive skew determined variant spread through the number of dispersing offspring produced.
28 Moreover, group augmentation increased potential spread because under constant population size
29 fewer units existed. Hyper-successful variants in emigrants could flood the breeding positions of a
30 smaller effective breeding population size and thus contribute disproportionately to the next
31 generation. The social systems with highest variant spread were characterized by male biased
32 dispersal and monopolization on big multi-male-multi-female groups and female- or male-biased
33 dispersal with cooperative breeding where the alpha female could access the units' full reproductive
34 potential through cooperative care. Genetic diversity was mostly affected by the number of
35 immigrants in units and the total number of units. The more group sizes increased through
36 philopatry, the fewer number of distinct philopatric lines in different units there were, decreasing
37 diversity. The more groups increased through immigration, the higher the inequality. Because
38 philopatric lines always gathered at least 50% of genetic contributions, immigrants shared the rest. If
39 there were more immigrants, each of them gathered less. The social system inducing the highest
40 genetic diversity was characterized by a population of monogamous pairs while the lowest had
41 highest multi-male-multifemale groups with only a monogamous pair reproducing. Overall, our
42 model supports previous frameworks and empirical studies linking stronger sexual and social
43 selection with faster adaptive and neutral anagenesis but is less suited to test for cladogenesis. We
44 propose some evolutionary speed scenarios according to previously reconstructed social transitions
45 in different taxa.

46 **Keywords: Social evolution; Social dimensions; Anagenesis; Cladogenesis; Evolvability**

47 Introduction

48 Sociality can influence evolutionary speed from two main effects. Firstly, it constructs a sort
49 of niche that triggers new selective pressures that produce change (West-Eberhard 1979,
50 1983). Due to the nature of social selection being among two or more evolving creatures it
51 should induce coevolutionary feedback-loops between the characters affording success in
52 social competition and the responses of conspecifics towards these characters (e.g.
53 preferences). Because characters mediating social success are key determinants of fitness
54 and because trajectories of coevolutionary loops are likely to diverge in different parts of the
55 population, social selection might reduce gene flow. Thus, social selection should induce
56 both changes in characters involved in social competition through coevolution and induce a
57 fragmentation of the population. Secondly, because social selection is coupled with
58 reproductive skew in many animal societies, the number of individuals reproducing becomes
59 smaller than the carrying capacity of the environment, sometimes to a staggering degree
60 (Crozier 1979; Wilson 1992). Such a reduction in the number of reproductive individuals
61 decreases the effective breeding population size (N_e). Because N_e is reduced, the role of
62 chance in determining shifts in gene frequencies should increase (Kimura and Crow 1963).

63 While the above accounts indicate that when increasing social selection, evolution should be
64 affected, let's go deeper into the implications. On the one hand, coevolution should increase
65 the speed of change in characters mediating social competition. Because these are likely to
66 include anything from body size to physiology, ornamentation and cognition, we can assume
67 increased social selection should induce change overall. The arguments that link strong
68 social selection favoring drift through reduced N_e should also likewise predict change, albeit
69 this might affect more strongly neutral regions of the genome. At the same time, the
70 fragmentation of the population through reduced gene flow indicates higher probabilities of
71 isolation and thus speciation.

72 In a parallel study, Socias-Martínez and Peckre (2023) have reviewed the theoretical and
73 empirical evidence for a link between social and sexual selection and evolutionary speed.
74 The authors have shown that the rationale of the above studies can be extended, and more
75 concrete predictions made by contemplating social variation from a multidimensional
76 perspective. Social systems have been described as containing at least four dimensions by
77 Kappeler (2019): Organization describes which sex disperses or remains philopatric and the
78 average number of males and females per social unit. Structure captures the equitability of
79 conflict and cooperation for access to resources; it maps the unbalances in benefits obtained
80 and costs paid by different individuals living in a society. Mating systems describe the
81 distribution of mating and genetic parentage in social units. Lastly, the care system informs
82 how each sex takes the burden of care for offspring, including the presence or absence of
83 helpers. If one contemplates this dimensions and some of their interactions, it appears that
84 previous research on evolutionary speed and sociality can be enriched substantially.

85 Social systems' effects beyond selection strength and N_e

86 It exists today an unexplored set of mechanisms when evaluating the consequences of social
87 systems for evolutionary speed. Beyond social/sexual selection strength and changes in N_e ,
88 the different social dimensions represent patterns and constraints on the capacities for a
89 new variant to replicate and spread, and to which extent different matriline and patriline
90 get to mix. This perspective wasn't investigated previously, with the exception of a model by
91 population geneticists that targeted effects of sociality on heterozygosity, the excellent work
92 by Parreira and Chikhi (2015). This vacuum in sociobiology is probably due to the focus on
93 individual fitness and lately on kin selection that characterized the field in the last decades.
94 Also, the characterization of animal societies into different dimensions has been a long
95 process that needed recognizing different aspects of animal social lives and their importance
96 and that is still being refined and rethought.

97 But how do these social "patterns" of gene replication and mixing affect evolutionary speed?
98 I will illustrate this first with an "extreme" example of variation in the **mating system**.
99 Polygyny and polyandry might both result in the same N_e if the sum of reproducing males
100 and females is equal. However, if we assume biases in parental investment being higher in
101 females, a polygynous species will produce more offspring. If each female produces 10
102 offspring on average, then, polyandrous social units will produce 10 offspring only while the
103 polygynous species will produce 10 per female. Furthermore, while in both systems one of
104 the individuals monopolizes reproduction, because the number of offspring might differ
105 strikingly, the potential contribution to the next generation of one individual is far greater in
106 polygyny. Now one could argue that this is not the case because different social units of a
107 species have more or less the same productivity. Producing 10 offspring by a polyandrous
108 unit among a total of 100 in a population with ten units is equivalent to producing 100
109 through polygyny amidst 1000. The relative contribution to the next generation of polygyny
110 and polyandry would be equivalent.

111 Here is what differs from perspectives based only on the number of reproductive individuals
112 (N_e), i.e., if we add social selection: Let's imagine a new mutation arises and should be
113 inclined to spread because its beneficial to his/her carriers. If it is so beneficial that it makes
114 it more probable to become alpha breeder, then the equivalence in contribution to the next
115 generation between both mating systems breaks. If we have a mutation likely to be placed in
116 the breeding position, when this mutation arises in a polygynous system it can theoretically
117 spread much faster than in a polyandrous one. It can do so because the offspring of the
118 alpha individual are also likely to have the advantage and become alpha and are more
119 numerous. Because of this superiority in numbers of advantageous offspring in polygyny, the
120 contribution to the next generation is no longer equivalent between both mating systems.
121 Thus, we could expect polygynous species to change faster anagenetically than polyandrous
122 ones.

123 Now, this effect on the speed of spread of a new mutation is not limited to the mating
124 system but conditional on other dimensions of the social system. **Social organization** is likely

125 to have a decisive effect, specifically the **dispersal regime**. The difference between polygyny
126 and polyandry is likely to become exaggerated if sons are dispersing in polygynous systems
127 because they are likely to amplify their spread by reproducing at the same rate than their
128 father did in a new unit. If instead daughters disperse, there should probably still be a
129 difference because they will be more numerous dispersing than under polyandry, but the
130 spread will be much lower because they will only produce a limited number of offspring in
131 each of their new units.

132 The **care system** is also likely to play a role in this potential spread. For example, all the
133 above contrasting predictions between polygyny and polyandry apply to taxa where females
134 make the highest parental investment and are severely limited in their potential offspring
135 productivity compared to males. They do not necessarily apply, and might be reversed in
136 taxa where females can increase the number of offspring by mating with several males as in
137 some oviparous taxa with paternal care (Kokko and Jennions 2008; Royle et al. 2012). These
138 predictions also do not necessarily apply to species where female productivity can be
139 drastically increased through the help of beta individuals like in eusocial or cooperative
140 breeding species. Under such conditions polyandry could be associated with extremely high
141 offspring production and thus the difference with polygyny would be cast doubt upon.

142 Social structure could also play a role if female productivity is impacted. For example, if
143 polygynous units are traversed by a strict female hierarchy, while the productivity of the
144 alpha female might be increased because she gains improved access to key resources, the
145 total unit productivity might decrease compared to an egalitarian unit. This is also likely to
146 arise because of the negative consequences of stress on fertility (Dunbar and Shultz 2021a,
147 b) related to group size and aggression.

148 In addition to the anagenetic effects of social variation, there might be **cladogenetic effects**.
149 For example, increased gene spread by a successful mutation as suggested above should
150 induce a “brassage” of the population that could prevent speciation from ensuing.
151 Nevertheless, there are social systems that could have even higher brassage and it does not
152 necessarily include those with high reproductive skew. For example, those systems where
153 most individuals reproduce at a similar rate, like monogamy or polygynandry should be
154 mixing and maintaining a higher diversity than either polygyny or polyandry. This higher
155 diversity maintained by a relative absence of reproductive skew is likely to impose
156 constraints on speciation because if individuals emigrate and mix regularly, the
157 fragmentation of the population needed to catalyze speciation is unlikely to appear. All
158 those social dimensions generating reproductive skew, for example a care system with
159 cooperative breeding and a social structure with hierarchies might reduce mixing and
160 increase the chances of populations fragmenting reproductively and thus speciating more
161 often.

162 Why a shift from focusing on the process to accounting for the pattern?

163 The existing framework arising in the 70s focused on the positive or neutral selection
164 processes deriving from individual selection in a social context. The predictions we just made
165 on anagenetic and cladogenetic effects are instead based on a focus on the structure, on the
166 pattern generated by animal societies. Both are necessarily the same thing looked from
167 different angles but this shift in focus could limit our ability to test previous ideas. Despite
168 this pitfall, we think it is capital to address the constraints or chances that societies impose
169 on gene replication and mixing to understand evolutionary speed. Important variation on
170 the anagenetic and cladogenetic potential of animal societies not addressed by traditional
171 accounts based on social selection and **Ne** could be discovered.

172 Importantly, gene replication and mixing patterns of animal societies might persist were
173 social selection does not as social systems have been shown to have high degrees of
174 phylogenetic inertia (e.g., Peterson and Burt 1992; Ligon 1993; Shultz et al. 2011; Opie et al.
175 2013; Kappeler and Pozzi 2019). Such inertia could indicate that even if the selective
176 pressures that made social systems of a kind arise change or disappear the structures
177 conformed persist. More pragmatically, these structural effects of animal societies might be
178 easier to model than those of social selection strength and communicative systems and **Ne**
179 and drift.

180 Profiting from this different situations, we here offer an investigation of the effects of
181 different gene replication and dispersal as well as genetic mixing patterns arising from social
182 variation on evolutionary speed using computer simulations. I will try to provide answers to:
183 which social systems dimensions are more prone to produce pheno-/geno-typic change?
184 Which ones to produce speciation? Are the two evolvabilities linked?

185 Materials and methods

186 Model constants

187 Simulations were carried out using R software (v. 4.3.0) and code is available at
188 https://github.com/llsociasmartinez/Social-systems_Evolutionary-speed. The model was
189 based on a single social unit that we followed over three generations. Although a 3-
190 generation snapshot perspective seems at first short for our problem, if we can find
191 differences between social systems at this time scale, it could hint to potential effects over
192 evolutionary timescales and stimulate the choice of species to compare in future studies.

193 The social unit was characterized by two sex (female and male) and rank classes (alpha and
194 beta). Each sex could only have a single alpha individual. Females had a limited number of
195 offspring set to the arbitrary number of 10, with even sex ratio at birth. Males could
196 potentially produce as many offspring as mating afforded. Each individual had 10 genes, 5
197 coming from the mother and 5 from the father (but see section “Taxa simulated” for
198 variations). For each simulation we varied parameters defining different social systems
199 dimensions (see section “Social variables”) that determined how sex and rank classes
200 reproduced. We collected information on two proxies for evolutionary speed throughout

201 these simulations in order to compare the scores for each social system (see section
202 “Evolutionary speed proxies”).

203 To make results comparable between social systems with different numbers of individuals
204 the simulated social unit was replicated to conform a population with “almost” constant
205 size. This population size was set as to afford all dispersing offspring from the alpha
206 individual of the most productive social system with the biggest group size to find a new
207 social unit. It corresponded to 6250 individuals because a unit with the biggest group size
208 simulated counted 50 individuals, females produced 125 dispersing offspring and a
209 population with 6250 can be divided into 125 of such social units. Because scaling odd and
210 even group sizes to the same exact population size through an integer number of units is not
211 possible, we first obtained the ratio between a simulation’s group size and the desired total
212 population size which coded the number of social units to attain it. We then rounded this
213 ratio and used it to replicate the social unit. Because we rounded the ratio, total population
214 sizes differed slightly between simulations (range 6204-6250, mean 6232.47, median 6233).
215 Depending on the proxy for evolutionary speed, this differences were corrected differently
216 (see section “Evolutionary speed proxies”).

217 *Social variables*

218 We modified the following social systems variables before calculating the evolutionary speed
219 proxies: **1)** the sex that dispersed (male or female), **2)** the number of males and females that
220 a social unit contained (all combinations of male and female group sizes from 1 to 25), and **3)**
221 the level of reproductive monopolization by the most successful male and female (0, 0.5 and
222 1). Regarding reproductive monopolization, a value of 0 reproductive monopolization meant
223 that the total number of offspring produced by the group was distributed equally. When the
224 monopolization value was different from 0, it had different effects on each sex. If the alpha
225 male monopolized reproduction with a 0.5, it meant that he got his “normal” share (as per
226 when the value was 0) plus 0.5 of the share of every beta male. When the value was 1 it
227 meant all offspring was sired by the alpha male. If the alpha female monopolized
228 reproduction with a 0.5, it meant that each other beta female in the group only produced
229 half its potential offspring. When 1, only the alpha female reproduced. We further included
230 4) cooperative breeding/eusociality by transforming the decrease in beta female
231 reproduction into the alpha’s own production. This 4th element can be understood as the
232 presence of cooperative care. Thus, the model simulated variation in social organization
233 through the unit composition and sex-biased dispersal, the mating system through the unit
234 composition and the levels of reproductive monopolization by alpha males and females, the
235 social structure through the negative effects of reproductive monopolization on female
236 output and the care system through the presence or absence of cooperative care and
237 reproductive monopolization by females.

238 *Taxonomic representation*

239 All simulations with social variables were carried out for three groups of animals that gather
240 most studies regarding sociality, namely mammals, birds and Hymenoptera (Rubenstein and

241 Abbot 2017). To do so I simulated social variation under diplodiploidy and haplodiploidy.
242 Under diplodiploidy, all individuals had 10 genes and obtained 50% from each parent. Under
243 haplodiploidy, males had 5 genes only and they were obtained 100% from their mother. We
244 modelled what could be understood as mammalian-like taxa by combining diplodiploidy
245 with male-biased dispersal (Mabry et al. 2013), bird-like combining diplodiploidy with
246 female-biased dispersal (Végvári et al. 2018) and Hymenoptera-like by combining
247 haplodiploidy with male-biased dispersal (see references cited by Johnstone et al. 2012 in p.
248 792).

249 *Evolutionary speed proxies*

250 *Anagenesis*

251 The potential for anagenesis was assessed with a measure of how fast the most successful
252 variant possible could spread. To assess this spread we calculated the percentage of genetic
253 contribution to the 3rd generation of an alpha individual of the dispersing sex in the 1st
254 generation. Because in haplodiploids with male dispersal this quantity is 0, we assumed an
255 origin in an alpha grandmother and followed her sons' reproductive contribution to the 3rd
256 generation. Specifically, we counted the number of genes grandpa or grandma had
257 transmitted to their grand offspring born outside the social unit. We divided this
258 contribution by the total gene production of the population at large. Because of the difficulty
259 of scaling different group sizes to an equal population size, we used the ratio between the
260 desired population size and the group size as a non-integer. By multiplying this non-integer
261 total number of units by gene production within a single unit we obtained a total population
262 production unaffected by rounding the number of units and still meaningful. The obtained
263 measure between 0 and 100% is directly interpretable as the extent of the spread in the
264 total population.

265 We assumed that the focal grandparent carried a variant that made all his/her offspring
266 dispersing become alpha breeder. Although under sexual reproduction such assumption
267 means that the alpha grandparent was homozygous for the new mutation, it simplified the
268 way we could account for half of the dispersing offspring that wouldn't have had the
269 mutation. This simplifying assumption means that we overestimated to some extent what
270 half of the dispersing offspring would do under standard sexual reproduction.

271 *Cladogenesis*

272 The potential for cladogenesis was measured through a proxy that assessed how many
273 different genetic lines reproduced in each generation and their relative contributions in
274 terms of gene numbers. To get hold of both the number of lines and their contribution we
275 used a diversity index. We chose to use Shannon-Wiener index because it is widely used in
276 evolutionary biology and ecology and it is one of the more robust (Jost 2006). We used the
277 Hill numbers of Shannon entropy, which are an exponentiated version of the traditional
278 index because these improve comparability when the number of categories, here the genetic
279 lineages, differ between samples (Chao et al. 2014; Konopiński 2020) as it likely does in

280 different social systems. Hill numbers give an equivalent in number of lines that would have
281 contributed equitably further improving interpretation and comparability (Jost 2006).

282 To have a measure at the population level and not the social unit we calculated the
283 Shannon-Wiener index on a sample that contained a repetition of the results for a single
284 unit. The number of repetitions was calculated by dividing the desired total population size
285 to the unit group size. Because repeating a decimal number of times was not possible, we
286 rounded to the greatest integer smaller than the obtained ratio, which represented the
287 number of units in the population. Because of this rounding, total population sizes differed
288 slightly among social systems. To account for this differences, we divided the alpha diversity
289 Hill number obtained by the simulation's total population size and multiplied by 100. The
290 obtained measure gives a percentage indicating the relative part of the population that has
291 contributed equally to the next generation. Thus, this measure of diversity is directly
292 interpretable and allows for comparisons between different social systems.

293 Results

294 Anagenetic and cladogenetic proxies are negatively correlated

295 The potential for variant spread and the alpha genetic diversity were strongly correlated
296 (Non-normality of variables and ties in ranks led to use of Kendall's rank correlation, $z = -$
297 150.27 , $\tau = -0.546$, $p\text{-value} \ll .00001$, see Fig. 1). The figures show that different social

Figure 1 | Relationship between anagenetic and cladogenetic speed proxies :

On the left panel a scatterplot relates the spread of hyper-successful variants on the x axis and the alpha diversity of reproduction at the population level on the y axis. The spread is calculated as a % of the total production of genes at the population level contributed by descendants of the focal alpha individual in a given social system. The Hill numbers of Shannon-Wiener diversity index indicate an equivalency to a number of lineages that would have contributed equally to the next generation in a given social system. Since it was divided by the population size it represents the percentage of the maximum theoretical diversity that could be obtained (i. e. every individual was an independent line and contributed equally to the next generation). On the right panel, the same relationship is explored but here the rank of the measures described previously were used and illustrate the data that served to calculate the Kendall's rank correlation.

298 systems either induce small values of both proxies or high values of one of them but not
 299 both.

300

	Proxy	Dimension	Test	group1	group2	n1	n2	Statistic	p	p.signif
1	% spread	Organization	Dunn	fm	mff	9	216	1.2e+00	2.4e-01	ns
2	% spread	Organization	Dunn	fm	fmm	9	216	5.2e+00	2.2e-07	****
3	% spread	Organization	Dunn	fm	ffmm	9	5184	3.4e+00	6.6e-04	***
4	% spread	Organization	Dunn	mff	fmm	216	216	1.4e+01	2.8e-45	****
5	% spread	Organization	Dunn	mff	ffmm	216	5184	1.1e+01	4.6e-26	****
6	% spread	Organization	Dunn	fmm	ffmm	216	5184	-9.0e+00	2.1e-19	****
7	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	monog	pgyn	625	1200	-3.5e+01	5.3e-263	****
8	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	monog	pandr	625	1200	4.6e-01	6.4e-01	ns
9	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	monog	promisc	625	2496	-3.7e+01	4.6e-302	****
10	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	pgyn	pandr	1200	1200	4.2e+01	0.0e+00	****
11	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	pgyn	promisc	1200	2496	1.3e+00	1.8e-01	ns
12	% spread	Mating system	Dunn	pandr	promisc	1200	2496	-4.8e+01	0.0e+00	****
13	% spread	Ploidy	Mann-Whitney	mammal	bird	5625	5625	2.0e+07	3.3e-142	****
14	% spread	Coop. breeding	Mann-Whitney	0	1	16875	16875	8.8e+07	0.0e+00	****
15	% spread	Ploidy	Mann-Whitney	wasp	mammal	5625	5625	1.4e+07	9.1e-19	****
16	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	fm	mff	9	216	-2.3e+00	2.4e-02	*
17	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	fm	fmm	9	216	-5.9e+00	4.7e-09	****
18	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	fm	ffmm	9	5184	-5.3e+00	1.3e-07	****
19	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	mff	fmm	216	216	-1.3e+01	3.3e-37	****
20	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	mff	ffmm	216	5184	-1.4e+01	1.4e-46	****
21	% max diversity	Organization	Dunn	fmm	ffmm	216	5184	3.3e+00	8.8e-04	***
22	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	monog	pgyn	625	1200	3.2e+01	1.2e-228	****
23	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	monog	pandr	625	1200	-7.3e-01	4.7e-01	ns
24	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	monog	promisc	625	2496	3.5e+01	6.7e-267	****
25	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	pgyn	pandr	1200	1200	-4.0e+01	0.0e+00	****
26	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	pgyn	promisc	1200	2496	-8.9e-01	3.7e-01	ns
27	% max diversity	Mating system	Dunn	pandr	promisc	1200	2496	4.5e+01	0.0e+00	****
28	% max diversity	Ploidy	Mann-Whitney	mammal	bird	5625	5625	1.4e+07	3.5e-27	****
29	% max diversity	Coop. breeding	Mann-Whitney	0	1	16875	16875	1.5e+08	2.0e-08	****
30	% max diversity	Ploidy	Mann-Whitney	wasp	mammal	5625	5625	1.1e+07	2.2e-148	****

Table 1 | Results of statistical tests for the effects of single social variables :

The significance and relevant statistics for each conducted test are displayed. Concerning social organization, 'fm' indicates pairs, 'mff' one-male-multi-female, 'fmm' multi-male-multi-female and 'fmm' one-female-multi-male units. For mating systems 'monog' codes for monogamy, 'pgyn' for polygyny, 'pandr' for polyandry and 'promisc' for promiscuous. For sex-biased dispersal, 'mammal' indicates male dispersal while 'bird' female-biased. Concerning ploidy, 'wasp' codes for haplodiploidy and 'mammals' diploidy. In coop. breeding, '0' indicates no gain by female alpha from beta females not reproducing and '1' a gain. Social organization and mating systems were tested using Dunn's test while the rest using Mann-Whitney U tests. For the latter, Holm's corrections were applied.

301 Social organization: One-male-multi-female units induce highest anagenesis while pair-living
302 induces lowest cladogenesis

303 When regarding social organization in the absence of cooperative breeding, the medians for
304 potential spread of a hyper-successful variant are overall very low (range 0.32-0.04% of
305 genes in a population). Despite this, some social systems might go up to 33%, and we will
306 investigate their specificities when regarding interactions between variables in a next
307 section. The highest median for spread is found in one-male-multi-female units, followed by
308 the multi-male-multi-female, the one-female-multi-male and lastly the pair one-male-one-
309 female (medians: 0.32, 0.24, 0.16 and 0.04 respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus, depending
310 on the social organization contrasts of up to eight times faster spread are to be expected.

311 Now let's look at the effects of social organization, in the absence of cooperative breeding,
312 on the Hill numbers of alpha diversity of genetic lines' contribution. Remember that values
313 indicate an equivalency to the number of genetic lines that would have contributed equally
314 and then were converted to a % of the highest possible value, i.e., every individual in the
315 population contributed equally and constituted a different line. The highest median number
316 of lines is found in pair-living units, followed by one-female-multi-male, one-male-multi-
317 female and multi-male-multi-female (100, 22.7, 17.7, 16 % respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2).
318 Thus, **pairs** have between 6.25 and 4.4 times more genetic lines contributing to the next
319 generation in a population of similar size than the other social organizations and should
320 therefore be expected to have the **lowest cladogenetic speed**.

321 Mating system: Polygyny induces highest anagenesis while monogamy lowest cladogenesis

322 When regarding the effects of the genetic mating system on potential spread, in the absence
323 of cooperative breeding, the overall contribution to the next generations within the
324 simulated conditions is very low but there are extreme outliers. Polygynous units have the
325 highest median, followed by monogamous, polyandrous and finally promiscuous (or
326 polygynandrous) units (0.67, 0.56, 0.21, 0.08% respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus,
327 polygynous units have between 8.36- and 1.2-times higher spread than the other mating
328 systems and should be expected to change faster when a new mutation arises.

329 Promiscuous units have the highest median alpha diversity, followed by polyandrous,
330 polygynous and monogamous units (21.2%, 14.4, 10, 7.6 respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus,
331 **promiscuity** generates between **1.5 and 2.79 times more diversity** than other mating
332 systems and should **speciate less often**.

333 Dispersal regimes: Male-biased dispersal induces higher anagenesis and cladogenesis

334 Under diplodiploidy and no cooperative breeding, **male-biased dispersal induces a median**
335 **spread 4.59 times** as big as that of female-biased dispersal (medians 0.38 and 0.085%
336 respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus, for example, **mammals are expected to change more**
337 **rapidly than birds**, at least when looking through the lens of which sex disperses. Regarding
338 diversity, **female-biased dispersal** induces a **higher diversity, 1.19-times** that of male-biased
339 dispersal

Figure 2 | Effects of social organization, mating systems, sex-biased dispersal, coop. breeding and ploidy on the evolutionary speed proxies:

Rows gather each of the two evolutionary speed proxies, top for % variant spread and bottom for the % of maximum possible diversity in contribution to the next generation. Each column gathers one of the social variables, from left to right, social organization, mating systems, sex-biased dispersal, coop. breeding and ploidy. Y axes represent the values for the proxies of evolutionary speed (median values per group are displayed as labels in red) while x axes the different values for the social variables. For social organizations, 'fm' indicates pairs, 'mff' one-male-multi-female, 'fmn' multi-male-multi-female and 'fmm' one-female-multi-male units. For mating systems 'monog' codes for monogamy, 'pgyn' for polygyny, 'pandr' for polyandry and 'promisc' for promiscuous. For sex-biased dispersal, 'mammal' indicates male dispersal while 'bird' female-biased. Concerning ploidy, 'wasp' codes for haplodiploidy and 'mammals' diploidploidy. In coop. breeding, '0' indicates no gain by female alpha from beta females not reproducing and '1' a gain. Finally the results of statistical tests are signified by a bar connecting the two groups tested and stars indicating the level of significance. Social organization and mating systems were tested using Dunn's test while the rest using Mann-Whitney U tests.

341 (medians: 21.6% and 18.1 for female and male-biased respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus,
342 for example, **mammals would be expected to speciate more rapidly than birds.**

343 Care system & Social structure: Cooperative breeding induces higher anagenesis while mildly
344 reducing cladogenesis

345 Cooperative breeding induces a **3.45-fold increase** in median **spread of a hyper-successful**
346 **variant** for all taxa combined (medians: 1.07 and 0.24% for cooperatively breeding and not
347 respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). All else being equal, **cooperative breeding taxa should change**
348 **faster than non-cooperative taxa.**

349 Social systems without cooperative breeding have a **mild 5.8% increase** in the **diversity** of
350 contributions to the next generation (16.3 and 15.4% for those with cooperative care and
351 those without respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus, **cooperative breeding taxa should**
352 **speciate more often**, albeit with a very mild difference to those without cooperative care.

353 Ploidy: Diplodiploidy results in higher anagenesis and slower cladogenesis

354 Under male-biased dispersal, **diplodiploidy induces an 0.079-fold increase** in the median
355 **potential spread** relative to haplodiploidy (0.38 and 0.35% for diplodiploid and haplodiploid
356 respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus, **mammals are expected to change slightly faster than**
357 **Hymenoptera** under equal conditions.

358 **Diplodiploidy** also induces an **increase in median diversity of 44%** compared to
359 haplodiploidy (medians 18.1 and 12.6% respectively, Table 1 & Fig. 2). Thus, **haplodiploid**
360 **taxa should speciate faster** than diplodiploids.

361 Mechanisms behind social systems effects on anagenesis

362 Now we proceed to a deeper level of analysis by looking simultaneously at the variation in all
363 the parameters investigated. First of all, we can see that those social systems with the
364 highest potential spread are those characterized by diploid organisms with the biggest group
365 sizes of both sexes where all females can reproduce equally with a single immigrant male
366 (Fig. 3, panel "a" male alpha total monopolisation, column mammal, top row polygyny
367 without female alpha monopolization). Compared to the analysis based on single variables
368 carried previously, we can see an additional effect based on the presence of beta individuals
369 that do not reproduce. To further understand what is triggering the observed patterns, we
370 will now start a descent from this peak by investigating how each variable pushes the values
371 of spread down the hill. We will refer to the social system with the highest potential spread
372 as the **mammalian monopolized mm-mf** (for multi-male-multi-female) throughout the rest
373 of the results.

374 *Number of dispersing offspring produced*

375 **Reducing the number females** in the mammalian monopolized mm-mf has a **negative**
376 **impact** on the **potential spread** of an advantageous mutation. This effect arises because
377 females **determine the number of dispersing sons** a male alpha sires in a unit. Females are
378 the limiting factor in terms of productivity. **Less adult females** result in **less numerous**

379 **dispersing descendants** of the alpha male. Because a less numerous bulk of offspring goes
380 into the population, **fewer alpha positions are taken by them**. As a consequence, the
381 relative contribution of the focal lineage to the new generation is lowered. This female group
382 size effect is drastic, we can see a decrease from approximately 21.6% to 1.2% when going
383 from units with 25 females to those with only 2. Thus, for **each female removed** from the
384 mammalian monopolized mm-mf, the spread of the new variant is **reduced 0.84% points on**
385 **average**. But consider that the effect appears non-linear with removals at higher group sizes
386 inducing stronger reductions in % of spread (see values of contour lines in (Fig. 3, panel “a”
387 male alpha total monopolization, column mammal, top row polygyny without female alpha
388 monopolization).

389 A **similar effect** is found when the **female alpha reduces the productivity of the unit** by
390 impeding beta females to fully reproduce or to reproduce at all (Fig. 3, compare top row
391 where mammalian monopolized mm-mf is found with the other two rows that progressively
392 increase the female alpha monopolization). For example, if we compare the mammalian
393 monopolized mm-mf with 20 females where all of them reproduce to the same group size
394 where female alpha cancels 50% of offspring produced by other females, we see a spread of
395 14.1% versus 9.1%. Thus, **for each dispersing son the alpha female impeded a beta to**
396 **conceive, the spread was reduced 0.11% points**.

397 **Other conditions** can also drastically **reduce the number of dispersing offspring** produced
398 by the alpha individual. If as we did for **haplodiploids**, the **focal alpha** was a **female** instead
399 of a male, she could not access the full replication potential of the unit as a polygynous male
400 could. The female alpha **produced the same number of dispersing sons regardless** of the
401 number of males and females in the group and the levels of reproductive monopolization.
402 This effect arises from the **differences in reproduction assumed between sexes**, where
403 females were limited while males could potentially fecundate all females in a group. This
404 applies to most taxa where females take care of their own offspring but **not necessarily to**
405 **taxa where females can increase the number of offspring by mating with males that will**
406 **take the burden of care** as in many oviparous taxa (Kokko and Jennions 2008; Royle et al.
407 2012).

408 Because in **bird-like taxa modelled**, the number of dispersing daughters is **also limited** by
409 **what the alpha female can produce herself**, the same constraints are found. For example,
410 let's consider a bird social system that is a “mirror image” to the mammalian monopolized
411 mm-mf, a monopolized lek with non-reproducing beta females (Fig. 3 panel “b”, see bird
412 column top row panel b female alpha total). Under our model conditions, the female alpha
413 will have more fathers to their offspring, but she will still only be able to produce 5
414 dispersing daughters. Moreover, these daughters will themselves only produce 10 offspring
415 each, further limiting their relative contribution to the next generation when compared with
416 the dispersing sons in the mammalian monopolized mm-mf, each siring 250 offspring.

Figure 3 | Effects of dispersal regime, group size and reproductive monopolization on alpha genetic diversity and potential spread of new variants :

Y axes represent variation in female group size, X axes male group size. Blue and red colors represent a gradient from low to high values of % of maximum genetic contribution diversity, our proxy for cladogenetic speed. Contour lines encode the % of spread of a hyper successful variant, black indicating lower values and white higher values. Each panel represents a different sex holding exclusive access to the other in the group for reproduction (a. male, b. female, c. none). Rows represent variation in reproductive monopolization by the other sex. For example, in panel a. we can see different types of female alpha monopolization of reproduction in the group, from one where female alphas reproduce at the same extent as beta females (top row, pgyn for polygynous, none for no monopolization), through an intermediate level of monopolization where beta females produce only 50% of their baseline reproduction (pgyn, medium), to full monopolization where beta females have no offspring equating monogamy (monog, total). Panel b. shows the corresponding scenarios when the alpha female monopolizes. Panel c. shows the various combinations of partial monopolization from each sex. Columns represent results for different taxa simulated characteristics, wasps and mammals with male-biased dispersal (former haplodiploid latter diplodiploid) and birds with female biased dispersal and diplodiploidy.

419 There is **hope for alpha females** to gain access to the **full reproductive potential of the unit**,
420 though. Under **cooperative breeding**, if other females do not reproduce themselves, their
421 parental investment is redirected and added to the female alpha productivity. Because of
422 this, when we again compare our mirror images, the mammalian monopolized mm-mf to the
423 bird monopolized lek with non-reproducing beta females, **if we add cooperative breeding**
424 **to the bird** or to both, the **differences in spread with mammals disappear** (see panel a Fig.
425 4, top row for mammal panel “a” vs. top row for birds in panel “b”).

426 But if this is true, **why** would then be **differences between taxa** were we followed the
427 **dispersing offspring of the alpha female?** (i.e., bird-like and wasp-like). First, because the
428 **dispersing offspring** was of **different sex**, the daughters for birds and the sons for wasps.
429 Thus, under cooperative breeding, the **level of monopolization by the alpha female affected**
430 **birds** of the 1st and 2nd (i.e., dispersing) generation while it did only to the 1st for **wasps**.
431 Likewise, in terms of productivity, the level of **male monopolization only affected wasps**
432 through the **dispersing sons**. These differences implied that when the alpha female did not
433 monopolize reproduction entirely, but male alpha did, bird daughters suffered lower spread
434 in their new units while Hymenoptera sons did not (Fig. 3 panel “a”, compare middle row,
435 wasp versus bird column). The reverse is true as well if we now consider a case where alpha
436 female monopolized reproduction, but the alpha male did not (Fig. 3 panel “b”, compare top
437 row, wasp versus bird column). In the latter case, dispersing sons benefited from landing
438 onto units with more females and less males with whom they had to share.

439 The **second source of differences** between **bird and Hymenoptera** social systems arose this
440 time from the **ploidy associated with each sex**. This difference could be due to either wasp
441 **haploid dispersing sons only contributing** to the next generation through **granddaughters**
442 while bird daughters contributed to both males and females **or** because a **Hymenopteran**
443 **population** produces **75% of the genes** a **diploid population** does. The former
444 mechanism should reduce the level of potential spread in Hymenoptera compared to birds
445 for an equivalent social system. The latter should benefit Hymenoptera because under the
446 same number of dispersing offspring, these contribute to a future generation that has a
447 lower total gene productivity in the denominator. The graphics suggest that when both
448 Hymenoptera and birds have access to the full potential of their units (i.e., both male alpha
449 and female alpha monopolize reproduction), wasps have higher potential spread. To tell
450 apart, we investigated the gene transmission chains for a social system with cooperative
451 breeding, monogamy and the highest group sizes for both sexes (i. e., Fig. 3, panel “b”
452 bottom row, bird and wasp columns upper right corner of plot). We see that in terms of
453 transmission of the genes from the grandmother there is no difference in quantity between
454 wasps and birds, or mammals. The fact that **sons produce only granddaughters** in wasps is
455 **cancelled by** the fact that **all genes transmitted by dispersing sons come from the**
456 **grandmother** as sons are haploid. If we compare the total productivity in terms of genes, not
457 of number of offspring, we see that wasps have 75% the value of birds. Thus, **wasps have**

458 **higher gene spread than birds and mammals** for a social system with a similar transmission
459 because they **contribute the same to a gene pool that is $\frac{3}{4}$ the size.**

460 *Number of breeding positions available in the population*

461 The previous section has showed how the productivity of the alpha has access to determines
462 the number of emigrant sons or daughters going into the world and that this is key to
463 understand how social systems affect the potential spread of a new variant. Nevertheless,
464 **we still see variation** within conditions **where the number of dispersing offspring is fixed.**
465 For example, when only the alpha female reproduces with the male alpha (Fig. 3, bottom
466 row panels “a” and “b”), when we follow the dispersing offspring of the alpha female (Fig. 3,
467 columns “wasp” and “bird”), or when female group size is constant but male group size
468 varies (Fig. 3, panel “a”). It seems that **the contribution to the next generation of a focal**
469 **lineage is dependent** not only on how many offspring go into the world but **also how many**
470 **other units are out there.** To make our comparisons between social systems with different
471 group sizes, we scaled all of them to a **fixed total population size.** Under such conditions, the
472 **more adults per unit,** the **lower the number of social units** at the population level. For a
473 similar pie, the bigger the portions the lower their number. Fewer units resulted in fewer
474 alpha positions available. Given that we modelled a **hyper successful mutation,** the
475 dispersing offspring **took over all alpha positions challenged.** If we consider a situation
476 where the number of alpha positions taken by dispersing offspring was constant, increasing
477 group size made **dispersing offspring secure a bigger proportion of the available alpha**
478 **breeding positions.**

479 If we start again with the **mammalian monopolized mm-mf,** we see that contour lines are a
480 function of female group size because they define productivity as discussed in the previous
481 section. We see also that if we decrease male group size, the potential spread decreases as
482 well, albeit with a lower strength. **Each male removed decreased the potential spread by**
483 **0.5% points on average** even though **they did not contribute to reproduction.** If we
484 compare this effect to that of females, we see that each female removed decreased the
485 potential spread by 0.8% on average, 0.3% points more than males. Thus, **increasing group**
486 **size** in the absence of any benefit can nevertheless **influence the spread** of a new mutation
487 **solely through the reduction of the number of social units** in the population.

488 While the effect of the number of social units at the population level is present in all
489 simulations, it is most visible when other sources of variation are constant, but group size
490 varies. In Fig. 3 panel “a”, we see several graphs with diagonal contour lines that describe an
491 increase in potential gene spread as an additive function of male and female group size. If
492 we look carefully, we see that these correspond to situations where the productivity by the
493 focal alpha individual is constant, the same number of offspring goes into the world but
494 where group size changes.

495 *Mechanisms behind social systems effects on cladogenesis*

496 The simulations show **enormous variation** in terms of **number of genetic lines contributing**
497 **equally to the next generation** measured through Hill numbers of Shannon-Weiner index
498 (alpha diversity hereafter). The **highest value, 100%**, corresponds to 6250 different genetic
499 lines, the entire population size contributing equally to the next generation. This value is
500 26.45 times bigger than the lowest value. The **highest alpha diversity** is associated with
501 **diplo-diploid monogamous pairs** and the **lowest** corresponds to the **biggest group sizes** for
502 **haplo-diploids** with **complete monopolization by the male alpha**. Under our rationale,
503 **monogamous pairs should speciate less often than other social systems**.

504 An **important difference** between this section and the previous is that the potential spread
505 was focalized on one unit and how well its descendants did while here, alpha diversity has
506 **two levels of analysis**, the **diversity within a unit and** how it translates to the **population**
507 **level**. Furthermore, alpha diversity will be affected by both the number of different genetic
508 lines that reproduce and the equitability of their contributions, both quantities increasing
509 the diversity index score. To understand how sociality affects these quantities, let's proceed
510 similarly to the analysis made in the previous section by walking down the hill of monogamy
511 in birds or mammals, the social system with the highest value.

512 *Number of genetic lines reproducing*

513 First of all, let's remember that when **adding individuals from the philopatric sex**, the
514 number of **genetic lines within a unit does not change** as we considered them being the
515 same line due to **relatedness**. So, starting with a socially monogamous bird or mammal
516 population, adding males in the former or females in the latter leaves the number of genetic
517 lines per unit unchanged. In contrast, **adding immigrants increases the available genetic**
518 **lines within a unit** because we considered them as unrelated and each coming from a
519 distinct line. So, adding females to the bird units or males to the mammalian ones leads to
520 an increase in the available lines within each social group. From this assumptions we can
521 predict several effects within social units. First, **whether groups enlarge through**
522 **immigration or through philopatry might induce contrasting differences for diversity**, the
523 former increasing the number of lines. **Second**, these increase in the number of lines will be
524 **mediated entirely** by the extent to which the **alpha immigrant individuals monopolize**
525 **reproduction**. The more monopolization, the less the available immigrant lines will manage
526 to contribute to the next generation.

527 But how do changes in the number of genetic lines reproducing within units translate to the
528 population level? If we start with a monogamous pair, let's first consider the **easiest**
529 **scenario**, where the **immigrant alpha individual monopolizes entirely** reproduction. It is the
530 easiest because adding new individuals, whether immigrants or residents changes the
531 number of lines available but does not affect the number of lines reproducing within a unit,
532 they stay at two. This example will allow us to see the effect of changing the number of lines
533 without the confounding effects of their reproduction. Strikingly, when **increasing group size**
534 **of either sex, alpha diversity at the population level decreases** (see diagonal color areas in

535 Fig. 3 panels “a” and “b” bottom row, as well as panel “a” “wasp” and “mammal” columns
536 and panel “b” “bird” column). The relationship is the same for all systems where the alpha
537 immigrant monopolizes reproduction, polyandry for birds, polygyny for mammals and
538 Hymenoptera or those for all taxa were only the alpha breeding pair reproduces. Under such
539 circumstances **adding a new individual** to the group from 1 to 25 results in a **loss of 3.85% of**
540 **the maximum possible diversity**. However, this relationship is not linear, each new
541 individual added has a milder negative effect on diversity than the previous one.

542 How can we explain these reduction in diversity given that the number of lines reproducing
543 within each unit and the population size stays the same? As we have seen in the previous
544 sections, **increasing group sizes reduces the number of social units** at the population level.
545 So, if the number of lines reproducing stays at two within each unit, **fewer units will result in**
546 **fewer lines reproducing overall**. But why are the effects **non-linear**? When we go **from pair-**
547 **living to units with three** individuals under a constant population size, we need to **tease**
548 **apart a third of the pairs** in the population to build the threesomes in the rest. Now, to
549 change from **trios to quartets**, we need to **deconstruct a fewer number of trios**, because
550 each contains more individuals. From four to five we need to destroy even less units to
551 rearrange them into bigger ones **and so on**.

552 Finally, adding immigrants can also increase the number of lines if the population had groups
553 with more than one resident. This is because to form the social unit with +1 immigrant, some
554 units have to be broken and all individuals which conformed the resident line become
555 immigrants (Fig. 5, follow long-dashed line with orange dots and positive effects when
556 adding an immigrant, green dot). Thus, all individuals which accounted for 1 line now might
557 be counted as several lines. This effect is non-linear, and the first immigrants added have a
558 much stronger positive effect on diversity because splitting is then done on units with more
559 immigrants which rearrange into new units without affecting their status as a different
560 genetic line (Fig. 5, see decreasing magnitude of positive effects of green dots).

561 *Equitability between reproducing lines*

562 Besides the number of lines reproducing, their relative contributions also affect the alpha
563 diversity index. The more unbalanced their contributions, the lower the diversity. Within a
564 unit, because all residents count as one line, all their scores get aggregated into a single
565 score. The **unbalance** is thus unlikely to be due to residents. On the contrary, **when adding**
566 **immigrants**, if the **alpha immigrant does not monopolize reproduction**, these have to split
567 the relative contribution of the unit. Because they are more numerous and each constitutes
568 a different line, their relative scores decrease. Because of sexual reproduction (at least
569 partial in haplodiploids), the resident line always gets 50% (75% for Hymenoptera) of the
570 reproduction in a unit. Immigrants on the contrary will each get a smaller share of the other
571 50% (25% for two, 12.5% for 4 and so on).

572 The consequences of adding immigrants to the alpha diversity is twofold. First, still at the
573 level of a single social unit, the diversity index should increase with each line added but

574 should decrease because of getting away from equality. At the level of the population, our
 575 simulations show that **adding immigrants** to an original pair-living population **decreases**
 576 **diversity** (see color gradient in Fig. 3, panel “a”, bird column, top row or panel “b” wasp and
 577 mammal columns top rows, Fig. 5, top short-dashed line with green dots). This effect is not
 578 due to a reduction in the number of lines reproducing at the population level. If we add only
 579 immigrants, that reproduce equally, the number of genetic lines in the population when
 580 changing group size stays the same. This decreasing diversity is **solely due to contributions**
 581 **becoming more and more unbalanced**. Each individual striped from a pair to form a trio will
 582 still reproduce, same for trios split to form quartets and so on. The **average loss** on % of max
 583 possible alpha diversity through inequality resorts to **2.56% points per immigrant added**.
 584 Nevertheless, the effect is again non-linear, and we can see that each immigrant added has a
 585 smaller negative effect.

586

Figure 5 | Effects of group augmentation through immigration or philopatry on genetic diversity :
 x axis shows the social unit group size, y axis the % of maximum diversity. Three different group size augmentation processes are shown, corresponding to a philopatric increase (green dots, short-dashed top line), an immigrant increase (orange dots, long-dashed bottom line) and both simultaneously (blue dots, solid middle line). On top of the latter baseline augmentations, at each group size we added either one more immigrant (orange dot) and/or one more resident (green dots). The changes either positive or negative on the diversity are shown nearby each dot. Lines connect the previous group size with the result of an augmentation.

587 Discussion

588 Our results support claims by West-Eberhard (1979, 1983), Bush et al. (1977) and Crozier
589 (1979) on the role of sociality to determine evolutionary speed. The present simulations
590 showed that social systems vary dramatically in the two proxies for evolutionary speed here
591 investigated. The results clearly show that the different social dimensions interact to predict
592 evolutionary speed. Thus, they support claims for the need to measure multiple social
593 dimensions when linking sociality and evolution (Socias-Martínez and Peckre 2023). Social
594 systems' dimensions affected evolutionary speed through few underlying variables including
595 1) the number of dispersing offspring an alpha could sire and 2) of social units these
596 emigrants would encounter determining together the spread of a new variant; and 3) the
597 number of social units and 4) the number of immigrants reproducing in any unit determining
598 the diversity. Anagenesis and cladogenesis proxies were negatively correlated, but most of
599 their variation was concentrated at different group sizes. Importantly, variables that tend to
600 be taxa-specific such as sex-biased dispersal and ploidy had deep consequences for both
601 proxies implying that a comparative perspective is essential to understand social effects on
602 evolution.

603 Did our model represent social selection strength and Ne ?

604 Previous theories link increasing socio-sexual selection strength with anagenesis in
605 competitive characters through coevolution (West-Eberhard 1979, 1983) or drift (Bush et al.
606 1977; Crozier 1979; Crozier et al. 1989). Such anagenesis in characters mediating social
607 competition later results in cladogenesis because gene flow diminishes among different
608 parts of the population that evolved divergently. In the current model, social selection is
609 simulated through differential access to reproduction from alphas and betas. Such
610 simulations can represent contest or ornament-mediated competition as well as social
611 hierarchies impacting access to food resources resulting if these condition reproductive
612 success. However, the short timescale modelled, the absence of gene/character values and
613 social or sexual mate choice/competition imply that there was no coevolution nor drift
614 occurring in our model. The evolutionary process wasn't modelled here. Instead, a fixed
615 social system that imposed capacities and constraints for gene replication, spread and mixing
616 was used. The previous framework emphasizes the processes that ensue over time to
617 explain change and speciation while we measured the intrinsic capacities of different social
618 systems dimensions for gene spread and mixing at any time t . As we will discuss, though,
619 both perspectives might be equivalent.

620 Analyzing societies as a pattern rather than a process is certainly naïve because selection
621 might profit those mutations that are able to change the social system they inhabit to their
622 advantage and animals are not merely passive ends of society but individuals that can
623 modify their social environment. For example, a very aggressive female bird might be able to
624 monopolize several males to reproduce with, even if she was raised in a pair-living unit.
625 Despite this power of the individual, some evidence, both from behavioral research and from
626 phylogenetics suggests that social behavior is plastic but within certain limits at any given

627 time. For example, pair-living monogamous mound-building female mice (*Mus spicilegus*)
628 show decreased reproductive success when housed in polygynous units (Gouat and Féron
629 2005). Similarly, social systems show high degrees of phylogenetic inertia in a world that has
630 changed ecologically and for lineages that have entered new ecological conditions (e.g.
631 Thierry 2008; Kappeler and Pozzi 2019).

632 *Anagenesis*

633 In previous frameworks like that for sexual or social selection the spread of a character that
634 makes an individual win a competition or be chosen as a partner is due to assuming his/her
635 offspring will inherit a high probability of winning or being chosen (reviewed in Socias-
636 Martínez and Peckre 2023). The current model somehow manages to capture this
637 phenomenon because reproductive success is reinforced in our simulations. We measured
638 how much a variant that already succeeded in becoming an alpha individual spreads through
639 offspring that themselves become alpha. So, in a certain sense we assumed that there was a
640 link between being in an alpha position, which would correspond to winning or being
641 chosen, and offspring being as likely to do so. For example, in our pair-living simulations, a
642 male that bred, a “chosen” male, had offspring that would find a mate. Same for a harem
643 holding male or a lek holding female. Thus the current model simulates a simplified version
644 of the coevolution suggested by West-Eberhard (1979, 1983). Perhaps because of the
645 equivalence to the coevolution suggested by previous frameworks, our results confirm their
646 predictions as well as agree with previous studies on sociality and anagenesis.

647 As predicted, increased social selection strength was associated with increased predicted
648 anagenesis. In our simulations, the mechanism underlying the link between social selection
649 strength and anagenesis depends on sociality allowing the alpha individual to produce more
650 offspring that go into the world. Such systems are characterized by reproductive skew. In our
651 model this corresponded to social units containing more females that reproduced with a
652 single or few males or to cooperative breeding allowing the alpha female to multiply her
653 output using betas’ workforce. These systems are characterized by great inequalities that
654 generate enormous selection pressures to become alpha. The number of offspring an alpha
655 can produce, compared to the rest of the population, is synonymous with how strong
656 selection will be to attain such a rewarding position.

657 This link between offspring production, social selection strength and anagenesis is further
658 amplified if the number of alpha positions in the population is scarce. The hyper-successful
659 offspring modelled take over a higher proportion of these positions as these become scarce.
660 Emigrants thus engender a higher proportion of the next generation. This is likely the case
661 when groups are larger, but alphas still get most of the reproduction. Such a situation is
662 equivalent to saying that reproductive skew at the population level, and thus also social
663 selection strength, are exaggerated because there are fewer breeding positions.

664 Now let’s dialogue with the other side of previous frameworks, that regarding neutral
665 evolution through the *Ne*. Again, sociality is supposed to reduce the effective population size

666 and that is supposed to erode diversity in neutral genes simply because chance has more
667 chances to politely invite some alleles to disappear. In this sense, while we have talked about
668 positive selection in the previous paragraphs, the fact that social selection strength is
669 expected to correlate with reproductive skew, whether through access to mates or
670 resources, means that many alleles that do not play a role in social competition will be
671 affected. Under reproductive skew, fewer breeders breed and so the effective breeding
672 population size is reduced. Drift should thus become coupled with positive selection and
673 induce anagenesis also in characters that are not being selected socially. This implies that the
674 predictions for anagenesis made based on the mechanisms discovered with the current
675 model and on coevolution also apply to regions not under social selection.

676 The above link between anagenesis and social selection is in accord with findings by
677 Fitzpatrick et al. (2012) in Pinnipeds and Wiberg et al. (2021) in an experimental population
678 of *Drosophila pseudoobscura* where higher levels of polygyny were associated with faster
679 anagenesis. In addition, cooperative breeding/eusociality fostered the potential for
680 anagenesis as in Crozier et al. (1989), Shell et al. (2021) and Chak et al. (2021) and did more
681 so when increasing the number of helpers as found by Schmitz and Moritz (1998) and
682 Dogantzis et al. (2018). Our results are also in line with sophisticated modelling endeavors by
683 Chevalier et al. (2022) and Gluckman and Bryson (2011). In the former, smaller mating
684 groups tended to slow down anagenesis. Chevalier et al. (2022) modelled gene-trait
685 evolution but as stated above, the link is strong with the way we modelled anagenesis.
686 Gluckman and Bryson (2011) found that the more severe the matrilineal hierarchies'
687 consequences for accessing resources, the faster the anagenesis. Anagenesis was faster in
688 genes that determined the efficiency of converting resources into offspring, and the
689 selection pressure was stronger at the bottom of the hierarchy. In a sense then, the
690 modelled phenomenon. To make the comparison possible, females would have traits that
691 allow them to climb the hierarchy.

692 Our results are in contrast with previous findings of polygamous species having faster
693 anagenesis than polygynous and monogamous ones in African cichlids by Seehausen et al.
694 (1999). This contrast regarding polygamy and polygyny might arise because of the use of the
695 social organization to predict the mating system and because this taxa has types of social
696 systems not modelled. The discrepancy can be somehow mitigated by translating the social
697 organization into a genetic mating system perhaps. For example, the definition of polygamy
698 implies males being chosen by unconstrained females as partners. The authors suggest this
699 removes the upper bound of the number of females that can reproduce with the more
700 attractive males. If a mutation arises that makes a male super attractive, reproductive skew
701 will unbalance towards him. In our model this could be similar to results on groups with high
702 numbers of both sexes but were only one or a few males reproduce with many females.
703 That's because even though the number of females is said potentially unbounded, animals
704 move through space and won't get to interact with the whole population. The constraints in
705 home range sizes are going to make an equivalent number of interacting individuals to the

706 social unit in permanently social taxa. This implies that our results might somehow translate
707 to solitary species depending on how these arrange their home ranges.

708 *Cladogenesis*

709 Our proxy for cladogenesis is a measure of how many lineages contribute to the next
710 generation and how equal their contribution is. Is this proxy related to previous frameworks?
711 In a certain sense it bears many resemblances to the concept of **Ne**, the effective breeding
712 population size. **Ne** establishes an equivalence in size with an idealized population that
713 follows Hardy-Weinberg assumptions (random mating, even sex ratio, no reproductive skew)
714 (Kimura and Crow 1963). Through different equations allowing to correct for violations in the
715 mentioned assumptions, one can “transform” or set an equivalence between a focal
716 population of study and an idealized population. Because the rate of change, i.e., neutral
717 evolution, can be predicted for the idealized population, after making the equivalence we
718 can do so as well for the real population at hand. The main idea is that the bigger the size of
719 the population, the longer diversity is maintained. Generally, when a population breaks the
720 Hardy-Weinberg assumptions, it is equated to a smaller population in the idealized scenario.
721 So, at the end of the day when reproductive skew increases, when sex ratio is uneven and
722 when mating isn’t random, diversity should be eroded faster and neutral anagenetic speed
723 increase.

724 Measuring the diversity of genetic contributions through Hill numbers conforms a similar
725 approach to the **Ne**. Hill numbers of diversity indexes allow to take a given number of
726 categories, each amounting to some quantity, and derive an effective number of them. The
727 effective number is an equivalent number of categories that would have contributed equally
728 (Jost 2006). In the present model, the categories were reproducing lines and their quantities
729 the number of genes produced. Thus, we obtained an effective number of breeding lines
730 without reproductive skew. Now, despite the model not representing space, because
731 different social units were modelled, mating wasn’t random. We controlled for this non-
732 randomness by aggregating the scores of individuals depending on relatedness before
733 calculating the effective number of breeding lines. Thus, we already reduced the population
734 size as the **Ne** conversion would do for an absence of random mating. We did not account
735 for the fact that genetic lines were sex specific and also for the absence of even sex ratios in
736 the population. Nevertheless, because of the overall resemblances I would assume that both
737 quantities, the Hill numbers and the **Ne** are correlated but further investigations are needed
738 to explore this possibility.

739 While establishing a correspondence between Hill numbers and **Ne**, we also cast some doubt
740 on the utility of using both proxies, given that anagenesis is related to **Ne** as well through
741 reproductive skew. Did we measure anything new? We can see in Fig. 1, 3 and 4 that both
742 proxies are negatively correlated. Nevertheless, each proxy shows most of the variation
743 where the other does not. At small group sizes, <10, most social systems have nearly null
744 spread. Interestingly, within these range diversity can go from 100% to 10%. On the contrary,
745 where diversity seems uniformly low, the spread of a variant can explode, from nearly null to

746 33%. As we have seen, effects weren't linear for any of the proxies and the non-linearity
747 seems reversed for each proxy. Diversity appears to respond strongly when group sizes
748 change within small values while spread does the contrary, changes most when group sizes
749 are at high values. In a sense, then, each proxy seems to have targeted something different.
750 The potential spread measures what could happen each time that a new advantageous
751 mutation appears, on the contrary, diversity measures the background change. Both forces
752 might be correlated though, and what the results seem to be saying is: in order to have a
753 mutation that can spread very fast you need first a social system where mating patterns
754 result in very low diversity. Then with each increase in group size you are exponentially
755 increasing the speed of such potential spread.

756 Now, our proxy was supposed to measure cladogenesis and not neutral evolution. We did
757 our best but cladogenesis seems like a hard fish to catch, especially with such a simple
758 model. Anagenesis and cladogenesis are supposed to be related, more anagenesis improving
759 the possibility that divergence results in reduced gene flow that results in speciation. Both
760 proxies should then capture cladogenesis to some extent. Now, they might also be somehow
761 unrelated because for example both polygyny and monogamy can maintain a population
762 "united" independently of whether this population changes more or less over time. If
763 individuals' migration allows for homogenization of different parts of the population, then
764 speciation will be precluded. Now if ecology or geography sets some blueprint for new
765 species, then the social systems predicted to have faster neutral or adaptive anagenesis
766 should become new species with higher probability, and this is likely to be the case in the
767 real world.

768 Given that we only have an indirect measure of speciation, our results are difficult to
769 confront with previous empirical studies. Parreira and Chikhi (2015), in a pioneering attempt
770 to link social systems and heterozygosity in mammals, designed a model with age and
771 reproductive classes that varied in the number of reproducing adults per sex and which sex
772 dispersed. Heterozygosity is a measure of gene flow that should be theoretically similar to
773 our genetic mixing based on alpha diversity. Now, a different number of individuals were
774 sampled within each social group depending on the mating system modelled but it was done
775 at random among the adults present. This implies that success in becoming breeder was not
776 repeatable nor heritable. Such fact positions the model far from the frameworks based on
777 coevolutionary anagenesis and social selection and close to our measure of alpha diversity of
778 the genetic contribution at the population level. In the absence of selection, their model
779 shows that sociality does not reduce diversity through drift but tends to maintain it. They
780 find that monogamy induces the highest diversity followed by polygamy, extreme- and
781 moderate-polygyny. Our results are to some extent in accord because monogamy, at least
782 under a pair-living social organization, induced the highest possible diversity. Now, if group
783 size increased monogamy became a doom for diversity because only a reduced number of
784 alpha couples reproduced. But, in the model by Parreira and Chikhi (2015), reproducing
785 "monogamous" couples were sampled at random from the adults in a group. Thus, even

786 with monogamy, all individuals could get to reproduce sequentially. Such a scheme would
787 correspond to polygamy/polygynandry in our model. If that is true then our results are even
788 more in accord as polygamy had the highest median diversity, followed by systems with
789 more reproductive skew.

790 Our results disagree with those of Iglesias-Carrasco et al. (2019) on the interactions between
791 body size, anagenesis and social organization to predict cladogenesis in an extremely diverse
792 set of bird species. The authors classified species according to their social mating system
793 (i.e., social organization) in an ordered variable from polyandry through monogamy to mild
794 and high polygyny to lekking/promiscuous and tried to predict cladogenesis. Given the
795 terminology and the PGLS model used, it seems that the authors think of sexual selection
796 strength as linearly increasing from polyandry to polygamy. Nevertheless, polyandry is an
797 imbalance as polygyny, and could theoretically be as strong a selective pressure, especially in
798 taxa where females can increase output by mating with males. Moreover, polygamy does
799 not necessarily stand as a stronger version of polygyny but could have a similar selective
800 strength as monogamy or lower. Further studies relaxing those assumptions could be
801 important to continue deepening into this important subject.

802 We also fail to show any indication that polygamous species should speciate more than
803 monogamous or polygynous ones as Arnqvist et al. (2000) found in insects. Now again
804 definitions might be responsible for discrepancies in results. In the latter example, mating
805 but not fertilization is counted, and the theoretical background rests on this fact. If several
806 males mate with a female, the sperm competition to be the one that fertilizes is supposed to
807 be the motor of anagenesis resulting in cladogenesis. Thus, if a male has such advantage, the
808 genetic mating system can go from polyandry to monogamy to polygyny depending on how
809 many females he can mate with and the strength of the advantage.

810 [Looking from a social evolution perspective](#)

811 The number of immigrants and of social units sets the long-term drift of a species, while the
812 reproductive capacity of units and the number of social units determine the adaptive bursts
813 it can make whenever a successful mutation appears. Now, sociobiologists think that social
814 systems do not mutate into other social systems randomly. Many are supposed to follow
815 step-wise complexifications from a putative solitary ancestor (Rubenstein and Abbot 2017).
816 Several well studied taxa such as ungulates (Takada et al. 2023), primates (Kappeler and
817 Pozzi 2019), ants, bees and wasps (Hughes et al. 2008), sapping shrimps (Chak and
818 Rubenstein 2019) and termites (Korb and Thorne 2017) seem to have gone through a
819 monogamous and many also pair-living stage first. While arguments in favor of kin selection
820 suggest this moment was characterized by homogeneity within social units, our model
821 suggests that at the population level such social systems maintain diversity. If ecological
822 pressures or competitive advantages induce group augmentation through offspring
823 philopatry or by immigration, diversity should decrease drastically. It would do so because
824 diversity responds the most to changes at the small ranges of group sizes. At this moment,
825 drift should become much faster, and species might change without necessarily adapting,

826 and even speciate. If groups continue to grow, on top of drift, social selection strength
827 should increase and induce positive selection on socially competitive traits. Then, only if
828 reproductive skew is present, either through polygyny with male-biased dispersal or through
829 eusociality/cooperative breeding even with female-biased dispersal, social selection could
830 result in anagenetic potential taking off.

831 Finally, if evolvability is driven by sociality and that sociality is in turn an evolving trait, could
832 it be that each step in social evolution had a different speed? We could speculate that if the
833 first step is a pair-living one, evolution takes place in a monogamous population with high
834 diversity and low potential spread. Thus, it might take longer to transition to other social
835 systems if they need adaptations to function such as increased communicative complexity
836 (Peckre et al. 2019). If transitions involve increases in group sizes, diversity will decrease
837 rapidly allowing further changes to occur much faster.

838 [On solitary social organizations](#)

839 Throughout the model we ignored solitary species. Nevertheless, the predictions here made
840 could hold for these species. The only change to make would be on how to convert
841 territoriality or home range overlap into a social organization here modelled. Perhaps the
842 area encompassed by the sex with the biggest home range during reproductive season could
843 be used as that defining the social unit. Within this area we might any combination of each
844 sex depending on the species, matrilineal or patrilineal kinship structures and even
845 hierarchies.

846 [Sex-specific assumptions](#)

847 Overall, despite going into exploration of significant variation, our model has a key
848 simplifying assumption, females have a limited number of offspring while males do not. This
849 was chosen to represent the fact that because of higher investment in anisogamy and care in
850 the taxa modelled, females would tend to have a limited number of offspring compared to
851 males. While both sexes could have all individuals from the other sex as mates, the output by
852 males could be disproportionately bigger than that of females. Our results reflect this and
853 could be understood as a model were “sex-differences predict sex-differences” with a
854 conventional assumptions (de Vries and Lehtonen 2023). Despite simplifying the model, this
855 assumptions about the care system make it biased and while capturing an important part of
856 the animal kingdom might not be representative of the mode of reproduction of many
857 oviparous taxa (Royle et al. 2012). Because eggs can be transferred to other individuals (a
858 guarding male in many fish and insects or an unrelated parent in brood parasites) (Royle et
859 al. 2012), limitation would be on the male side in such taxa. In such situations one would
860 need to reverse the male and female tag in our predictions as a starting point. Future models
861 and comparative studies need to take into account variation in the care system beyond
862 cooperative breeding which could offer new explanations for differences in evolutionary
863 speed consequences of sexual selection in different taxa (Kraaijeveld et al. 2011).

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